

Invest in Open Infrastructure

Arcadia Proposal

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Purpose (1-2 lines)

The purpose of this grant is to increase investment, adoption, and the sustainability of open technology to further research and scholarship.

Grant duration in months

36 months

Grant amount and currency

3,470,000 USD

Executive summary

[Invest in Open Infrastructure \(IOI\)](#) was founded with the belief that in order for open infrastructure to flourish, we need to advance our collective understanding and strategy for sustaining the sector.

Our aim is to marry research and analysis with coordinated action to shift the market towards open infrastructure and away from an over-reliance on for-profit, third-party tools. We believe that a change in strategy is needed to address the complexity in making open technology and infrastructure a competitive, durable, trusted, and cost-effective investment for the research enterprise.

To test this hypothesis, over the past year we've explored the core needs of institutional decision makers, infrastructure providers, philanthropic funders, and other supporting organizations to help identify where IOI can best address their shared pain points. For institutional leads, there's decision fatigue in keeping track of open infrastructure solutions, time constraints and budget pressures that affect open solutions from being seen as viable or competitive, and coordination challenges within and across institutions. This often leads to a prioritization of individual need over that of the collective good and selection of commercial solutions.

At the same time, philanthropies have been more actively exploring shifts towards investing in maintenance and development of shared infrastructure. The Siegel Family Endowment recently released a [white paper](#) declaring a new strategic focus for grantmaking dedicated to infrastructure, which will lead to an anticipated \$20M USD in grantmaking in 2021. Other foundations have been following suit, both in actively investing time and funds in building infrastructure, as well as asking questions about ongoing maintenance and impact of their investments.

We are asking the Arcadia Fund for three-years of support to scale the operational capacity of IOI. Additional staff and resources will accelerate our efforts to alleviate decision fatigue at institutions and meet information gaps with cutting-edge research, analysis, and guidance. Based on our research, we believe that coordinated action is critical today in order to drive investment to where it's needed most to advance open infrastructure, and improve the health of the ecosystem writ large.

Table of Contents

[Executive summary](#)

[Introduction](#)

- Year 1
 - [Activities](#)
 - [Outputs](#)
 - [Outcomes](#)
- Year 2
 - [Activities](#)
 - [Outputs](#)
 - [Outcomes](#)
- Year 3
 - [Activities](#)
 - [Outputs](#)
 - [Outcomes](#)

[Anticipated challenges](#)

[Our commitment to open](#)

[Impact](#)

Resources

- [Budget & Justification.](#)
 - *Note: Budget is attached.*
- [Current operational expenses](#)
- [Additional sources of funding](#)

Registration details (Code for Science & Society) - Attached

Letter of Determination

Latest financials

Recent 990

Current Board of Directors

Introduction

IOI exists to improve funding and resourcing for the open technology and systems that research relies on, in order to enable a healthy, sustainable ecosystem in line with the values of the academy and not one that is co-opted or controlled by commercial interests. We employ an evidence-based approach to guiding decision makers on where to invest, both within institutions and in partnership with other funders in the sector.

[We define open infrastructure](#) as the sets of open services, protocols, standards and software that the academic ecosystem needs in order to perform its functions throughout the research lifecycle — from the earliest phases of research, collaboration and experimentation through data collection and storage, data organization, data analysis and computation, authorship, submission, review and annotation, copyediting, publishing, archiving, citation, discovery, and more. *Open* infrastructure represents the narrower sets of services, protocols, standards and software that can empower communities to collectively build the systems and infrastructures that deliver new improved collective benefits without restrictions to participation, engagement, or usage.

The proposal below outlines a three-year strategy to advance our collective understanding and strategy for sustaining the sector. We envision a future where open infrastructure is robust, easily adoptable, and incentivized by the market. In this future, libraries, institutions, funders, and the broader research community act together as a powerful force to ensure that infrastructure is never a blocker to research, learning, and access to knowledge.

Activities (Year 1–3)

The activities, outputs, and outcomes detailed over a three-year planning arc in this proposal are organized around the following programmatic and operational objectives.

Providing strategic support & investment guidance, anchored in research & analysis. We provide strategic support for decision makers (e.g., funders, budget holders, institutional leaders, consortia, service providers) to help them assess, build, and invest in open infrastructure. We employ a research-driven approach to increase our understanding of the current landscape and sector to power this work, aiming to shed light on costs and models and analyze where investment would be more prudent and impactful for the greatest good.

Grow uptake and investment in open infrastructure by institutions and funders globally. A significant aspect of this work lies in coalition building and targeted outreach to institutions and funders to activate their interest, use of, and investment in open infrastructure. This involves relationship management and casemaking support to increase the uptake and build market share of open infrastructure in institutional settings. We will work to further develop strategies, coalitions, and communications to ensure we're both tending the existing network of invested parties and working to expand engagement.

Enabling collective, coordinated action. We convene key stakeholders to test and pilot solutions and to act together to advance the health of the sector and enact change.

Furthering a shared agenda for investment in open infrastructure. Increasing and sustaining open infrastructure investment at an ecosystem-wide level calls for global cooperation and coordination, among governments, funding frameworks, consortia, and aligned programs and initiatives working to advance openness and equity in research and scholarship.

Building organizational capacity and effectiveness to deliver on our mission. To achieve the objectives above, IOI needs to build operational capacity and functional governance to empower the organization to achieve our stated aim. This includes scaling our operational and research capacity through staffing, building a robust pipeline of support, building functional governance to support decision making, and further evolving our processes to ensure operational excellence.

In Year One, our core activities include:

<i>Objective</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>Add'l notes</i>
<i>Capacity-building</i>	Build IOI's research and organizational capacity through targeted recruitment, hiring, and evolution of project governance.	
<i>Strategic support & guidance</i>	Increase understanding of current landscape and costs to establish initial baselines.	<i>Priority areas: funding data, underlying development and maintenance costs for open infrastructure, map of existing capital sources, current landscape of providers.</i>
	Conduct needs analysis for key stakeholder audiences.	<i>Key audiences: infrastructure providers (to understand funding need, gaps), institutional leaders (to assess service needs, gaps and friction points), and funders (to assess priority areas for investment, means of measuring portfolio impact).</i>
	Establish draft criteria and framework for prioritizing open infrastructure needs, circulate for comment.	
<i>Grow uptake & investment</i>	Assess and identify gaps and institutional blockers for investing and choosing open infrastructure.	
<i>Coordinated action</i>	Scope initial structure and participation for an open infrastructure Technology Oversight Committee.	<i>This builds on our previous research and asks institutional leaders for decision making support and an accountability mechanism for service providers and vendors.</i>
	Convene monthly calls for key stakeholders and open infrastructure community.	
	Evaluate need and design for broader conference around open infrastructure, building off 2020 Joint Roadmap for Open Science Tools (JROST) Conference.	<i>JROST recently moved under IOI as a community event. We're currently evaluating the need for an annual</i>

		<i>conference vs smaller convenings, exploring options for 2021.</i>
<i>Shared agenda</i>	Map current players investing in open infrastructure and examine their roles in advancing the sector.	
	Begin work on a cross-walk of funding priorities for key open infrastructure investment programs.	

The activities specified above are crafted to help build out a strong foundational theory of change, process for evaluating need, and evidence-base to enable IOI to provide reliable, trusted investment guidance to meet the needs articulated at present by funders and institutional leads. This includes an assessment of available funding data, to inform our estimate of current investment from non-institutional funders, and shape our analysis and modelling of funding gaps and redundancies. Our initial research will also investigate the underlying costs for a selected number of core infrastructure services through a mix of qualitative and quantitative methods, including maintenance costs, growth and development, and other often unaccounted for expenses such as staffing and in-kind contributions. This also includes mapping existing pools of capital available to support open infrastructure and begin prioritizing for future research (e.g. institutional funding, governmental support, philanthropic funding, industry investment).

Years Two and Three will focus on refining that work, expanding thoughtfully as needed, and mobilize those recommendations towards tangible shifts in the sector. We’ve detailed anticipated activities, outputs, and outcomes below, noting that as each year’s work informs the next and is dependent on being responsive to emergent needs that may arise in the sector, research areas and work products may shift and adapt. We consider Arcadia a key thought partner for this work, and will engage you in the evolution of Years Two and Three as the work develops.

Year One outputs include items such as:

- A draft framework for prioritizing open infrastructure needs, including criteria for evaluating and assessing projects and providers, a defined scope to maximize effectiveness and ensure the greatest impact, and a draft set of indicators.
- Landscape analyses and resources that shed light on maintenance costs for select open infrastructures and current levels of investment from non-institutional funders (e.g., government, private and public philanthropies). Landscape analysis / resource list of open infrastructure providers, and mapping of key institutional supporters.
- Needs assessment for select infrastructure providers, institutional leaders, and funders.
- Shared principles and “better business practices” for open infrastructure providers and vendors from Open Infrastructure Technology Oversight Committee, building on community input.
- Regular conversation points for members of the open infrastructure community, to provide a place for sharing knowledge, common challenges, collaboration opportunities.
- Documentation to support Advisory/Steering Committee member selection, effective governance, onboarding/offboarding. Handbook and documented onboarding process for new hires.

Anticipated outcomes for Year One include an improved understanding and model of the flow of capital towards open infrastructure projects, funding gaps, and core development and maintenance costs. This helps us map our recommendations and evaluation process to advocate that existing resourcing be directed to where it's needed most (an element of this work that warrants its own research). The needs assessments will provide us with the concrete data points necessary to ensure we are designing our analyses and strategies to be maximally useful and implementable.

The framework for assessing open infrastructure needs will also provide an ecosystem-wide lens for exploring high-priority areas, which is not only beneficial for our work directly, but also provides the community of interested stakeholders with a higher-order view for their planning purposes.

Through targeted convenings ranging from monthly calls and the Open Infrastructure Technology Oversight Committee to another possible JROST event (note: we are actively discussing what sort of event would best advance the aims of this work and of the open infrastructure community), we will explore various modes of cross-institutional and cross-party dialog to support decision making and coordinated action. We will also begin work to assess gaps in institutional buy-in, participation and uptake of open infrastructure, to better inform work needed to build institutional market share and adoption through targeted outreach and campaigns.

In Year Two, our core activities will build on the foundational work conducted in Year One, and is expected to include the following activities. The work detailed below will focus on implementing the foundational work achieved in Year One, further expand our analysis and underlying research, and seek to implement our findings by aligning stakeholder groups to take action via targeted convenings and roundtables. We will also dedicate time to evaluate additional levers for incentivizing infrastructure providers and spurring investment from key decision making bodies and funders, including but not limited to establishing a collective fund to administer resources to projects in need.

<i>Objective</i>	<i>Year Two Activity</i>	<i>Add'l notes</i>
<i>Capacity-building</i>	Expand IOI's core team to scale our research capacity and address gaps in expertise surfaced in Year One, as well as build out dedicated support for strategic partners IOI is serving.	<i>This includes the hiring of an additional Research Analyst and a Relationship Manager, to support targeted strategic work with key decision makers and funders.</i>
	Initiate with IOI Advisory Committee regular evaluation of operational needs as they relate to organizational structure and sustainability.	<i>This includes assessing fiscal sponsorship vs incorporation; evaluating means to diversify and sustain IOI's work.</i>
<i>Strategic support & guidance</i>	Test application of framework for prioritizing open infrastructure needs; match with existing open infrastructure solutions.	

	Expand funding analysis to explore additional funding sources (e.g. institutional support, vendor reciprocity, government subsidy); regional and global representation; forecasting & trend analysis.	
	Continue research and modelling of “hidden costs” such as staffing and participation in developing and maintaining open infrastructure.	
<i>Grow uptake & investment</i>	Conduct an analysis on impact of IOI-led collective fund to incentivize further investment and health of the sector.	
	Generate recommendations and action plans for key stakeholder groups based on research and analysis to expand adoption and investment in shared solutions.	
	Assess health/sustainability of the ecosystem building on initial indicators crafted in Year One.	
<i>Coordinated action</i>	Convene smaller “roundtable” focused discussions to advance recommendations surfaced through research.	<i>Examples: Provost/Chancellor Council, vendor/industry roundtables.</i>
	Advocate for additional transparency, efficiency, equity, and reciprocity from vendors and infrastructure providers serving the ecosystem.	<i>This includes outlining values-aligned service providers, utilizing power of the collective to advocate for better terms, transparency, efficiency, rates, etc.</i>
	Convene regular calls for key stakeholders and open infrastructure community.	
<i>Shared agenda</i>	Collaboratively develop a shared roadmap and agenda for investment in open infrastructure for research and scholarship.	

In Year Two, we aim to have established and tested processes in place for assessing open infrastructure providers against defined priority areas, be generating recommendations, reports, and providing strategic guidance to help make a stronger investment case in open infrastructure, and to be a trusted convener of various groups to advise, align their interests, inform our models, and move towards broader impact.

Year Two outputs include items such as:

- Research findings and strategic guidance to inform our recommendations.

- Investment recommendations for open infrastructure based on the framework for prioritizing need and impact.
- A draft framework and scope for an IOI-led collective fund to support needs of the sector and incentivize further investment.
- Public communications such as use cases, blog posts, and position papers.

Anticipated outcomes for Year Two include a concrete understanding of what making an investment case for open infrastructure looks like as a product and a process, with additional insight to help validate our assumption about that being the best means to serve our core stakeholder audience. Quantitatively, we'll have additional data on usage, implementation, and potentially even funding and/or staff time reallocated. Qualitatively, we'll be able to gain a better understanding as to where additional iteration may be needed to ensure we're providing maximal benefit towards our defined key areas of focus and priority (to be defined in Year One). Our aims are to have test audiences across a range of investment types (e.g., institutional partners, philanthropic funders, government/federal funding) and metrics that will be informed and refined in Year One of development as we work with those communities to tailor a solution to address their unmet needs. We'll also increase our efforts to coordinate with aligned funding initiatives and programs working to dedicate resources to open infrastructure, to ensure our work is additive and amplifying wherever possible existing and adjacent efforts to sustain the open infrastructure ecosystem.

Year Two also focuses on catalyzing and mobilizing our research, recommendations, and strategies via smaller stakeholder discussions and groups like the Open Infrastructure Tech Oversight Committee. With this work, we aim to explore means to increase the awareness, buy-in, and coordinated action of key groups operating on the periphery of open infrastructure adoption and advocacy, such as Provosts and Chancellors, Faculty/Academic Senates, and vendors deriving financial value off of investment and productizing open infrastructure solutions. Through these targeted engagements, we will explore mechanisms to utilize collective power and coordinated efforts to further enact and accelerate change in the sector.

Lastly, the exploration of an IOI-led collective fund will further prepare us to understand where funding can and should incentivize further transparency, participation, and resilience for the open infrastructure ecosystem, and what our role should be in directly facilitating that through the dispersal of capital.

In Year Three, our core activities will focus on further iterating on and growing adoption of our core work products, such as investment guidance and strategic support to those with resourcing for open infrastructure. This year will also mark the fourth year of IOI as a staffed operation, and we anticipate efforts will shift to working with our Advisory and Steering Committee to evaluate and assess the effectiveness of our work to date, and explore pathways forward.

The work of Year One and Year Two will inform which direction IOI continues towards, be it as a consultant and support for institutional leaders and/or funding agencies, as a thinktank to provide research and strategic guidance for the sector, as a community-driven fund to further increase and bolster existing funding mechanisms for open infrastructure.

Objective	Year Two Activity	Add'l notes
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<i>Capacity-building</i>	Evaluate efficacy of current work, adoption rates, and impact on IOI’s future growth and sustainability.	
<i>Strategic support & guidance</i>	Explore additional research questions and audiences.	
	Generate recommendations and action plans for key stakeholder groups based on research and analysis.	
<i>Coordinated action</i>	Work to validate and enlist initial partners to further explore an IOI-led funding mechanism.	<i>Dependent on Year Two feasibility study and need.</i>

Year Three outputs include items such as:

- Research findings and strategic guidance to inform our recommendations; recommendations to evaluate for expanding (or retaining) scope of current framework.
- Investment recommendations for open infrastructure based on the framework for prioritizing need and impact.
- Pilot of IOI-led funding mechanism to incentivize further action (dependent on Year Two findings).
- Public communications such as use cases, blog posts, and position papers.

Anticipated outcomes for Year Three include a “productized” and fully operational research and strategy offering that institutions and funders utilize and rely upon to guide their investment. Additionally, we anticipate IOI’s work products and services to provide significant enough value to alleviate our reliance on grant based funding and present additional options to consider regarding the future of our work and business model.

By Year Three, we also anticipate that the scope and breadth of our work will have evolved to further address needs surfaced in the first three years of this grant, shifting our understanding of impact areas and priority needs.

Depending on the work of Year Two, we also aim to follow through on recommendations to further incentivize and enact lasting change, via mechanisms such as leading a community fund to drive additional investment and alleviate administrative barriers to collective funding as well as exploration of ways vendors and industry can help sustain the sector with appropriate safeguards (such as the recent announcement of the [Anaconda Dividend fund](#) to support the data science and machine learning communities).

Anticipated challenges

Building our organizational expertise effectively. This grant represents a significant growth opportunity and inflection point for IOI, in scaling from 1-2 staff members to 3-4 times that in a short period of time. We will rely on the support of our Advisory and Steering Committees to ensure robust recruitment and thoughtful onboarding, and utilize additional support and leadership from our fiscal sponsor, Code for Science & Society. We also recognize the challenges that exist in building a multidisciplinary team of

experts, and will look to draw from neighboring fields and domains to bring the best of finance, research, and business acumen to bear on this work.

Data availability and/or accessibility. Over the past year, we've worked to gather and model available funder data, as well as inquire about operating and ongoing costs for open infrastructure projects. While we've made headway in gathering initial data on funder investment, their quality, interoperability, and availability vary quite greatly. On the project and institutional investment side, costs are often distributed across a network of institutions and departments, fiscal sponsors, consortia, and other vendors/commercial partners which can make gaining an understanding of operating and ongoing costs for OI projects a challenge. There also can be a tendency for participants to withhold data for fear of public scrutiny, making trust and a culture where transparency is rewarded even more important.

To mitigate this hurdle, we will work with our network of institutional leads, funders, and infrastructure providers to outline approaches to solicit financial and resourcing data through collaborations with project leads and supporting organizations to the best extent possible so as to not hinder our research and analysis. We will also ensure that accessibility of data is part of our selection criteria for open infrastructure use cases.

Reconciling the global nature of research enterprise and the systemic inequities that exist in this work. A key consideration in our work to date, as well as moving forward, has been around scope. Concerns about how our work and recommendations will address the inherent inequities that exist in open source communities, higher education, and in funding are real, especially if we are advocating for longer-term investment in shared, open solutions to enable broader access and participation. We have consulted with DeEtta Jones and Associates to advise on a strategy for evolving our project governance to address inequities in global representation, racial and ethnic diversity, as well as expertise. In addition, we will explore at length questions about need and greatest impact in the design of our criteria and framework for prioritizing key areas of focus, so that we ensure to the best of our ability we are not exacerbating the inequities we seek to counter.

Assessing levels of funding and impact recommended funds will have. While we aim to do a deeper investigation into how best to assess appropriate and beneficial allocations of funding to high-priority OI areas of work, we also recognize that the financial stewardship and what's done with that funding is beyond our immediate control. We will look to other peers in this space to explore means of evaluating the impact of investment, including but not limited to follow on check-ins, reporting, and performance metrics.

Our commitment to open

IOI's work involves producing documents, databases, surveys and other landscape analysis tools, and conducting workshops and interviews with a wide range of stakeholders. All content will be made available under a CC-BY license with the exception of sensitive personnel and/or funding information. It is the stated goal of the IOI project that these outputs be participatory in nature and of use to the wider community.

We anticipate this work to lead to the production of blog posts to share out research progress, working papers/preprints (where appropriate), and supporting models and/or frameworks to supplement analysis. We also endeavor to share updates on this work openly with the community via our IOI Monthly Community Calls, which will be launched in the new year.

Written work, reports, analysis, and any videos will be made openly available under a CC-BY-4.0 license, and be made available on our website at investinopen.org. We will also explore venues to share this work that align with our values to provide openly available and accessible research, including but not limited to open repositories and preprint services such as Zenodo and the National Bureau of Economic Research.

Code that may be generated as a part of this work will be made openly available via IOI's Github repository under an MIT or BSD license. Data and models generated for this work will be stored securely and made available to the fullest extent possible under the terms noted above.

As information products are created, we will also work with Code for Science & Society to track those items to help further long-term sustainability and stewardship of any intellectual property created or held by IOI.

Impact

Our three-year strategy and build out plan detailed above aims to make open infrastructure a competitive, durable, trusted, and cost-effective choice for institutions.

This includes the following impact goals:

- Aligning power & influence across networks & programs, and shifting existing consortial and national funding models towards investment & stewardship of shared infrastructure.
- Building collective power through trusted peer networks to increase efficiency, accountability, negotiating power.
- Empower institutional leaders to take a more active role in directing pricing & terms for vendors and service providers.
- Shifting internal & external budgets towards shared needs, and directing funding effectively in measurable ways that combats the chronic underfunding of core open infrastructure services, and shifts power and influence away from commercial, third-party vendors.
- Increase the amount of funding and diversity of those investing in open infrastructure to ensure we're building towards a healthy, resilient, sustainable future for research and scholarship.

Budget & justification

The total ask for 3 years is \$3,470,253 USD. A complete budget breakdown is attached.

That is broken down across a couple of key areas, with phased recruitment and growth from Year 1 to Year 2, with more stable, consistent costs from Year 2-3. Further detail can be found below.

Top line costs include:

Staffing & Personnel: \$2,349,668 (with phased growth, detailed below).

Contractors & Professional Services: \$441,434

Travel & Meetings: \$166,510

Equitable participation: \$60,000

Overhead (15%): \$452,642

Estimated total: \$3,470,254 USD

Staffing & Personnel:

On the personnel side, our proposed budget would support the following roles (all of which would be new hires, outside of my salary line). Our cost estimate factors in fringe costs as well as 2-4% raises over the course of the grant.

Those roles include:

- Executive Director (Thaney)
- To be hired:
 - Year 1:
 - **Director of Research and Strategy** - strategic support for the Executive Director, overseeing project coordinator and research team, as well as research roadmap and execution.
 - **Engagement & Communications Lead** - to lead design of external communications and events (like JROST), monthly calls, higher level stakeholder engagement, and facilitation.
 - **Project Coordinator** - to support project execution, liaise with Directors and analyst.
 - **Research Analyst** - analytical support for costing and modeling work.
 - Year 2 & 3:
 - In Year 2, we would anticipate increasing our capacity in adding the following roles:
 - **Additional Research Analyst**
 - **Relationship Manager** - to support the Directors with business development, “client” relationships with institutional partners and funders, service management and ongoing stewardship.

Contractors & Professional Services:

In addition, we have budgeted \$441,434 for three years for Contractors & Professional Services. This is for shorter-term contract work around software development needs (for prototypes, dashboards, data pipelines), technical costs related to hosting and services (including supporting open source services we rely on); Professional services (for work with designers, legal and financial/investment experts for our work around collective funding and service models), and administrative assistance for project leadership.

This budget line increases in Year 2 to also enable us to contract with experts to examine business structures and possible incorporation needs for our ongoing sustainability and future beyond our current status as a fiscally sponsored project.

Travel & Meetings:

We’ve budgeted conservatively for Year 1 given the current pandemic, with support broken down for transportation & lodging for the team, and annual convening costs for events like JROST as well as Steering/Advisory/Working group engagement, as needed and given public health guidance.

Equitable Participation:

In addition to the costs named above, we have budgeted for Equity Sponsorship (ie., travel stipends) to help incentivize more equitable, diverse and inclusive participation in our work, knowing the ways in which volunteer labor limits the voices at the table. In addition, we’ve budgeted for honoraria and stipends to support participants in the open infrastructure Technology Oversight Committee that we’re working to stand up this year, following our Future of Open Scholarship work, as well as support speakers and experts for their engagement with compensation.

Overhead (Code for Science & Society):

This 15% is CS&S's standard charge. This fee covers comprehensive fiscal sponsorship, allowing CS&S to offer full project staff time positions with benefits, along with full financial administration, strategic, and administrative support.

Current operating expenses

Below is a summary of our current operating expenses, based on expenditures since the staffing of the project in mid-March 2020. Additional detail can be provided upon request.

Since March, the bulk of our operating expenses have gone to staffing and personnel costs for IOI's Executive Director and contractor support to rapidly scale our operations and research capacity during our initial months of fundraising. As we've shared with Arcadia in the past, IOI has been fortunate to receive financial support from a diverse set of institutions, consortia, and private and public philanthropies, which has enabled us to quickly meet the needs of the research community in uncertain economic times. Our choice to build capacity for our work through working with short-term contractors is very much a result of our initial funding, allowing us to be nimble and responsive.

Here is a breakdown of our key expenses by category, from March-Dec 2020 (all in USD).

- Personnel costs (including salary, taxes, benefits, payroll processing): \$133,148.8
- Program related consulting (contract-based engagements):
 - Programmatic:
 - Future of Open Scholarship project: \$41,125
 - Funding data prototype: \$15,000
 - JROST Conference: \$5,000
 - Operational:
 - Building anti-racist governance: \$10,000
 - Website redesign, illustrations: \$8,500
- Technical costs and services (including encrypted storage, website hosting, transcription services, equipment): \$3,290.68
- Administrative costs & overhead (including financial services and administrative processing, distribution of funds for JROST Rapid Response Fund, HR support): \$61,200

In addition to the cost breakdown above, we note the following anticipated contractor costs to be incurred in Q1 of this year (January-March 2021), as we conclude the Future of Open Scholarship project, an assessment pilot for the Arcadia-funded Next Generation Library Publishing project, and initial exploration of funding data begun last year. Additional sources of funding and expenditure related to new project work are noted under ["Additional sources of funding"](#).

- Program related consulting (contract-based engagements):
 - Programmatic:
 - Future of Open Scholarship project: \$13,875
 - Funding data prototype: \$5,000
 - Next Generation Library Publishing Assessment support: \$4,000
 - JROST Conference (video editing): \$750
 - Operational:
 - Strategic support (onboarding new staff, operationalizing research recommendations, communications): \$7,500

Additional sources of funding (Please describe the timeline, size and purpose of your existing or expected grants.)

Since last April, we have been fortunate to raise \$621,775 USD from a diverse set of funding sources, including (6) foundations/private philanthropies, (5) institutions, (3) library consortia / membership organizations, (3) nonprofits and infrastructure providers, (1) project-based contract. This includes \$50,000 USD raised to regrant as part of our Rapid Response Fund piloted at the end of last year, as well as support for key research and assessment services from institutional partners.

The figure cited above includes two new grants, as well as unrestricted operational support from Schmidt Futures (in the form of a matching grant), the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, and ongoing research support from the Libraries of the Big Ten Academic Alliance.

Those grants include:

- *Exploring hidden costs of open infrastructure (Mellon Foundation) - \$135,625 USD*

This 15-month grant (estimated to start February 2021 through May 2022) will support our initial exploration of the costs associated with ongoing maintenance, sustainability, and resourcing of the technology, tools, and systems that scholarship and research depend on. Funding will be dedicated in large part to bringing on a Research Data Analyst, whose work will be centered around building out a funding data prototype for the sector and further interrogating and analyzing the costs associated with running and maintaining key open infrastructures, building on initial findings from our Future of Open Scholarship research.

- *Invest in open infrastructure Summer Business Fellows: A Collaboration with Harvard Business School (Alfred P. Sloan Foundation) - \$36,850*

This shorter term engagement (January 2021-late September 2021) provides support for (2) paid 8-week internships for Harvard Business School students to build our capacity for economic analysis, modeling, and research by collaborating and pilot engagement with the Harvard Business School community. The research questions further explore areas of interest surfaced through our Future of Open Scholarship project by institutional leaders and research organizations to assist in their decision making and analysis, and build on modeling work we're currently undertaking with Kate Pugh of AlignConsulting and Columbia University.